

OPPORTUNITIES OF INTERNET IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN THE CLASSROOM

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7663214>

ELSEVIER

Foundation of Advanced Research Scholars

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Abstract: Nowadays. In this high-tech world technology is getting more advanced so that it impacts on every sphere of life including education, especially, learning and teaching English. Modern innovative technologies in the educational process increase the quality and effectiveness of education. In particular, there are several ways to use such information and communication technologies in learning and teaching a foreign language. Its advantages give important opportunity to make learning process more effective. The role of Internet in language learning and teaching is immeasurable. It is famously used all over the world that technical devices such as IWB, Smart phones, Internet, Apps are able to grab everyone's attention and respect since its great contribution in the achievement of learning and teaching language is limitless

Keywords: Internet, technology, distance learning, traditional teaching, pandemic, video courses, second language learning

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Received: 21-02-2023

Accepted: 22-02-2023

Published: 22-02-2023

Introduction. Today, Internet technology is the famous option not only for traditional but also for nontraditional learners. In the period of global pandemic, distance education via Internet and video courses is admitted to help learners in education system in distance. Practically, the Internet, with the capacity to connect users all over the world, has also been examined for its potential to help in the improvement of second language learner's skills. Results of a number of studies which were surveyed among language learners and teachers show that the Internet is revealed to have authentic and real language in a meaningful context, and as a result of observing this material, learners increase into creators of language rather than passive recipients. Usage of technology within the second language writing classroom also makes learner independent, is an excellent means for teaching foreign culture and language, and in general, positively influences students' attitudes which contribute to an overall greater (Ziyaboyeva Sevara Kazakova, 2018).

It is common statement that information and communication technology has impacted on the structure of language instruction not only in higher education but also in nursery schools so on and so forth. The benefit of the Internet and the wide spread of technology in our life and in our study are able to create new opportunities for language learning. Because of the fact that most of the Internet content is in English, teachers of English can take advantages of the enormous

variety of authentic materials relating to all spheres of life at almost no cost. Moreover, the content of all social media is in English which means that no matter learners have a chat which is not related in education or learning language, they unconsciously learn English by just having chat with friends. There are wide ranges of ways to learn English via Internet.

Methodology

The internet supports limitless quantities of authentic language resources, videos and worksheets, which are all available within seconds. Internet materials like videos, forums, and news sites are rich, fun and dynamic in ways textbooks so often are not funny and even they are considered to be boring.

It is proved that teaching English while students utilize the web provides opportunities for more independent learning which means that the teacher is giving them skills that they can use forever, furthermore he/she is teaching them how to choose something they need.

Results and Discussions

TED talks are considered to be designed to be fully informative, visually stimulating and have clear, take-away messages to listeners. In order to apply TED talks in the teaching English, videos can be used to be asked from students about some questions including to listen to the gist, answer comprehension questions, pick out target vocabulary, notice expressions, analyze presentation techniques, or discuss ideas. When English learners have watched a video, understood its language, and discussed its ideas, have them turn to the comments section on the video's web page. They can be asked to look for ideas that support or contradict the video's speaker, or have them respond to a comment they like or dislike. Obviously, they can not only improve their English but also they can expand their outlook by reading and responding comments of others. Vast majority of wonderful authentic language comes up in comments, and the comments on TED have tendency to be a little more concentrated. English learners can improve their speaking and listening by just watching and observing a You tube video a day. There are lots of useful, informative and effective videos on You tube channels such as "Bright sight", "Nas Daily", "VOA learning English", "Speak English with Vanessa" so on and so forth. Those channels provide very interesting and authentic content every day.

Second interesting way of using Internet to teach English is to have Internet chat activities. the most motivating chats which include interaction with native speakers are certainly chat activities for language students. There is a great number of ways that English learners can interact with guests. They can have interview guests about themselves, their country, their job, their family, and so on and so forth. Students can be grabbed to a debate or discussion about a given topic with the guest. Or else Students can also be interviewed by the guest; Obviously, English

learners can use What's App, Telegram, Facebook, Instagram and other famous social medias which people use them even million times in a day.

Google search engine can be probably useful for teachers in finding almost any kind of information on the Internet which means that Google has already created wonderful platform which contains any information on any topic. Teachers might have desire to try some of the following education related and generalized search engines. When teachers know how to find information online, they can create a bridge for their students to begin to step into this huge resource. Admittedly, there are a great number of websites which can provide with authentic and useful worksheets to download. For instance "<https://learnenglishteens.britishcouncil.org/>". In this website, teachers can access to download different and interesting worksheets to apply for their classrooms, the materials can be found on every level and every skill including vocabulary and grammar.

This skill is helpful to students not only for accomplishing their homework, but also as a survival skill in the modern workplace. Additionally, there some websites that offer online help from teachers for students who need aid with their homework. Teachers should know they search the quality of this homework help before recommending a website. There are also wide ranges of online resources specifically prepared to the needs of parents. Teachers who know these resources can suggest effective and useful websites to the positive school-home interaction.

Conclusion

All in all, the Internet has very strong impact on the development of the language teaching. Moreover, it can help to improve the e-learning and distance learning all around the world.

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